

Phase behavior of dense colloidal binary monolayers

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we study how structures develop on 2D dense binary colloidal monolayers as a function of the relative concentration of small/large particles. Translational and orientational distribution functions have been used to monitor the continuous phase transition through a detailed characterization of the global and local order. We have observed how a gradual enhance in the number of particles of different size leads to a continuous vitrification process, and how homogenous binary glasses forms in equimolar mixtures. On the other hand, we have performed a simple calculation that links the structures found with the pair dipolar potential, allowing the forecast of local structures in other arbitrary binary mixtures. Finally, we have corroborated the goodness of the binary systems as glass forming model by comparing the established scenario with the structural features found in partially aggregated monolayers.

INTRODUCTION

In general, two-dimensional (2D) crystals reproduce the main phenomenology known in their three-dimensional counterparts, both in dynamics and structure¹⁻⁵. The Mermin-Wagner theorem, however, establishes that strictly speaking crystalline order cannot exist in infinite sized 2D structures at non-zero temperatures^{6,7}. On the other hand, melting is not first order in the effectively two-dimensional world. 2D crystals, characterized by an algebraic decay of the translational order and a long range orientational order, undergo a continuous melting transition through an intermediate phase, the so-called hexatic phase, according to the predictions of Kosterlitz-Thouless-Halperin-Nelson-Young (KTHNY) theory. In the hexatic phase the particles have local hexagonal orientational symmetry, though the positions of the unit cells are slightly displaced from the assumed in the crystalline form. The positional crystalline order is destroyed by free dislocations in a dislocation-unbinding transition, and the intermediate hexatic phase exhibits a quasi-long-range decay of the orientational order with distance, and a short-range decay of the translational one. Subsequently, a second continuous transition is associated with the unbinding of dislocations into their constituent pair of disclinations, *i.e.* particles having a wrong number of nearest neighbors as assessed by a Delaunay tessellation. The resulting fluid presents typical exponential decay of orientational as well as translational order⁸⁻¹⁰.

In a different vein, glasses in 2D were observed by introducing some kind of geometrical frustration, polydispersity¹¹ or non-centrosymmetric interactions¹², into the crystalline system. The understanding of the physical processes giving rise to the general properties of glasses, both in 3D and 2D, probably remains as one of the most

interesting unsolved problems in condensed matter physics¹³. Glasses display all the mechanical properties of a solid but they exhibit a structure close to that observed in the supercooled liquid phase, *i.e.* no long range translational periodicity and certain degree of short-range order. The experimental behavior of glass formers near the glass transition presents some general trends regardless the chemical nature of the system¹⁴. On the other hand, 2D and 3D glasses present some common and universal features: No long-range translational nor orientational order, non-exponential relaxation functions as the system approaches from the fluid to the glass state, a frozen dynamics, *i.e.* a huge increase in the time scales as compared with the fluid state and dynamical heterogeneities. From the theoretical point of view the Mode-Mode Coupling theory (MMC) has been shown to capture the general features of simple systems (hard spheres, Lennard-Jones systems) undergoing the glass transition¹⁵. Probably the closest real model systems to those described by the MMC theory are the colloidal suspensions studied by Pusey et al.¹⁶ and by the group of Weitz^{17,18}. Constraining the system dimensions has been found to have a profound effect onto the glass transition temperature¹⁹⁻²². We have recently demonstrated, however, that the dynamic behavior of the glass transition in 2D systems (Langmuir monolayers onto the water/air surface) is similar to that described for the 3D ones²³. It is generally recognized that during the vitrification process, both the system structure and dynamics becomes progressively more heterogeneous and interdependent^{24,25}. Structure plays an increasingly complex role in determining the particle motion and local evanescent structures seem to be linked to the spatially heterogeneous relaxation and cooperative motions of particles. Therefore, a detailed knowledge of how the structure develops during the vitrification process is fundamental for understanding the relationship between the structural features and the dynamics. The study of the structure of the glass formation on binary

monolayers of colloidal particles was pioneered by the group of Rice²⁶. However the phase diagram of these systems is strongly dependent on the size ratio and the relative interaction strength between the particles. Therefore, more work is necessary to fully understand the phase diagram of 2D systems formed by mixtures of microparticles of different sizes and/or interaction strengths²⁷.

Main 2D crystalline, melting and vitrification features have been observed in atomic as well as macromolecular systems^{2,4,28-31}. 2D colloidal systems are ideal model systems for studying the universal properties of glass formation because of the easy accessible time and length scales, and the unhampered access to structural information. The theoretically predicted hexatic phase was confirmed for quasi 2D monodisperse colloidal system interacting via a soft centro-symmetric dipole-dipole potential, in both experiments and simulations^{2,3,32}. A question that remains unclear is whether continuous phase transition will be retained in a perturbed 2D solid. One way out could be to study first the continuous transition from crystal to a dense fluid or glassy phase associated with a monolayer of binary mixtures of different sized particles. The simplest polydisperse system is determined by two additional control parameters: the relative interaction ratio and the fraction ratio of the two different sized components. In consequence, the binary systems exhibit more complex phase diagrams, containing more diverse types of crystal structures and other interesting features not present in the monodisperse systems. Law et al. have found stable binary crystal structures for binary mixtures with large size ratios of like-charged particles interacting via a screened Coulomb pair potential³³. Maret's group has studied the solidification process of model glass formers by analyzing the structural and dynamical properties of binary monolayers formed by micron-sized superparamagnetic colloidal particles with different

susceptibilities. They found direct correlations between local structures and dynamical heterogeneities in this system^{29,34-39}. Substantial efforts were also made by studying 2D glasses through numerical simulations⁴⁰⁻⁴².

Despite these efforts, the disordering processes in 2D binary systems are not yet completely understood. Before the dynamical mechanisms can be established, we must characterize in detail the local and global particle configurations through which the system passes during the melting or vitrification processes. In this work, we will study the phase diagram of dense binary colloidal monolayers formed by different sized particles with similar surface charge densities. High enough coverages ensure a crystalline ground state in the corresponding monodisperse monolayers, for which we can systematically control frustration against crystallization by varying the relative amount of the different species. We will focus on how the dense amorphous structures develop on 2D vitrification when the relative concentration of small and large particles varies. A first step to solve this problem requires definitive experimental information on a set of partial pair distribution functions describing the particle configurations. Global translational and orientational order parameters offer direct information on the structural change during the process. We will discuss the occurrence of peaks in the distance-resolved pair correlations in conjunction with local arrangement. Finally we will relate in a simple manner the structures found to the minima in the interaction potential of the particles, and we will corroborate that other global disordered colloidal systems reproduce the structural features observed in the binary systems.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Our experimental setup has been described in detail elsewhere². Therefore, we only briefly summarize the essentials here. Our binary systems consist in different mixture of small s and large l polystyrene microparticles (Interfacial Dynamics, USA) with different sizes. The main part of this work is devoted to mixtures made up of particles with two different radii, $a_s=1.45 \mu\text{m}$ and $a_l=2.85 \mu\text{m}$. Towards the end, we present a complementary brief study in which the small particles are replaced by an even smaller $0.80 \mu\text{m}$ ones. Surfactant-free particles are negatively charged with sulfate functional groups on the surface and similar surface charge densities, $5.7 - 5.9 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ for the smaller ones and $6.2 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ for the larger particles. The spreading suspension is prepared by mixing 2-4 wt% binary aqueous suspensions containing different particle proportions with equal volumes of the spreading solvent (2-propanol, IPA). The latter is used as received from Sigma-Aldrich without further purification. After sonication for 30 minutes, small volumes (10-100 μl) are injected with a micro-syringe close to the flat interface made up of ultrapure Milli-Q water, with Total Organic Carbon (TOC) lower than 5-10 ppb and resistivity higher than $18 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and octane from Sigma-Aldrich previously filtrated trough an alumina (Al_2O_3) column. The system is then conserved at 25°C for 30 minutes. Once the thermal equilibrium is reached, the level of the interface is adjusted to the height of a steel ring set to hinder drift motions.

We have studied the structure of the formed monolayers using optical microscopy and digital imaging. Particles absorbed at the interface are visualized from above with an optical microscope (Nikon Eclipse 80-I microscope) provided with long-distance objectives 10x and 50x, at locations far away from the ring edge. Images are captured

with a CCD high speed camera (Hamamatsu, model C8800-21C) at full resolution, 1000x1000 pixels, and stored in a computer for the subsequent analysis. Hence, home-made software allows us to determine the area and the location of the center of mass of each spot in a sequence of binarized frames. From these data we evaluate several averaged statistical functions discussed below.

DATA ANALYSIS

Structural information of the binary mixtures adsorbed at the water/octane interface has been obtained through some correlation functions that allow quantitative measures of the degree of symmetry in the particles positions. The pair distribution function, $g(r)$, describes on average the probability of finding a particle at a distance r away from a given reference particle, relative to that for a completely random distribution at the same surface number density. Once the particle positions r_i are determined, the translational distribution function is calculated as

$$g(r) = \frac{1}{\rho^2} \left\langle \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \delta(\vec{r}_i) \delta(\vec{r}_j - \vec{r}) \right\rangle = \frac{A}{N^2} \left\langle \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \delta(r - r_{ij}) \right\rangle \quad (1)$$

where $\rho = N/A$ is the average surface number density of the particles in the monolayer. The averages are done over the N particles present in the field of view of area $A = 4 \cdot 10^4 \mu\text{m}^2$ (between 200 and 450 depending on the proportion of large and small particles in the mixture) and taking into account typically 5 independent particle configurations. Likewise, partial pair distribution functions for large and small particles, $g_{ll}(r)$ and $g_{ss}(r)$ respectively, account for the probability of finding particles of equal size at a certain distance r . Translational distribution were often used to analyze 2D glass

formers and crystal nuclei in binary monolayers of superparamagnetic colloidal particles under a magnetic field influence^{29,37,39}.

To evaluate the bond orientational order in the colloidal monolayers we must first define what is mean by a bond between two “near neighbor”. A common definition of nearest neighbors proceeds via the construction of Voronoi polyhedra with shared sides having equal distances to two adjacent particle center positions. Delaunay triangulation underlying the Voronoi tessellation allows evaluating the number of nearest neighbors of each particle, n , and the angle between the segments connects them. Hence, the local bond orientational order parameter is given by

$$\langle \Psi_6 \rangle \equiv \Psi_6 = \left\langle \varphi_{6,k} \right\rangle = \frac{1}{N} \left| \sum_{k=1}^N \varphi_{6,k} \right| \quad (2)$$

where $\varphi_{6,k}$ is defined by

$$\varphi_{6,k} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n e^{i6\theta_{kj}} \quad (3)$$

where the sum is carried out over the n nearest neighbors and θ_{kj} is the angle between an arbitrary axis x and the bond joining neighbors i and j . Ψ_6 quantifies the extent to which the bonds between k particle and its n neighbors present sixfold symmetry. Ψ_6 is 0 in the disordered liquid phase and close to 1 in a 2D triangular lattice. Analogous local order parameters Ψ_z can be defined to characterize other local z -fold symmetries. Finally, the bond orientational correlation function is defined as

$$g_6(\vec{r} - \vec{r}') = \frac{\langle \Psi_6^*(\vec{r}) \cdot \Psi_6(\vec{r}') \rangle}{\langle \rho(r) \rho(r') \rangle} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\Psi_6(\vec{r}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_k) \varphi_{6,k} \quad (5)$$

$$\rho(\vec{r}) = \sum_{k=1}^N \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_k) \quad (6)$$

and the star indicates the conjugate. According to the KTHNY theory the orientational correlation function $g_6(r)$ approaches unity in the solid phase, decays algebraically in the hexatic phase, and decays exponentially in the liquid phase.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At relatively high surface coverages structured monolayers of particles at the octane/water interface are observed (Fig. 1). The symmetry and structure of colloidal patterns are dictated by the nature of the constituent colloidal pair interactions. Although the origin of the pair potential between the particles trapped in the interface is not fully understood, the dominant repulsive term is believed to be due to the presence of residual dissociated charges on the particle's surface⁴³. These charges, asymmetrically shielded by two media with different dielectric constants, lead to soft dipolar repulsions. The repulsive pair interaction potential is given by⁴⁴:

$$U_{ij}(r) \propto \frac{Q_i Q_j}{r_{ij}^3} \xi_i \xi_j \quad (7)$$

Here, $\xi_i = a_i(3 + \cos \theta_i)/2$ represents the distance from the point charge $Q_i = \sigma_i A_{\text{sci}} f_i$ to the interface, where f_i is the dissociation degree of the charge at the aqueous phase and A_{sci} is the area of the spherical cap in contact with the aqueous phase. The latter depends on the contact angle θ of the particles as $A_{\text{sci}} = 2\pi a_i^2(1 + \cos \theta_i)$. The contact angles at the water/octane interface for the large and small particles are $\theta_l = 135^\circ$ and $\theta_s = 120^\circ$, as determined by using the gel trapping technique (GTT)⁴⁵.

The structure of binary colloidal monolayers is determined by a combination effect of four different parameters: the total surface number density ρ_t , the stoichiometry, *i.e.* the number ratio of the two different particles, the interaction between particles of equal size, U_{ss} or U_{ll} , and the dipolar moment ratio $m_{sl} \equiv \frac{Q_s \xi_s}{Q_l \xi_l}$. The total surface number density is defined as the sum of both number densities $\rho_t = \rho_s + \rho_l$, where the partial surface number density of the specie $i (i = s, l)$ is given by

$$\rho_i = \frac{N_i a_i^2}{A}, \quad (8)$$

and N_i is the number of particles of radius a_i .

In this work we study the structures formed in monolayers with a nearly constant surface number density value $\rho_t \approx 0.033$, but varying the proportions of small and large particles. In Fig. 1 we show microphotographs and their FFT analysis for the typical microstructures formed. The total coverage fraction, the partial percentages of the surface coverage defined as $\% \rho_i = \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_t} 100$, the number ratio $N_{s/l} = N_s/N_l$ and the number fraction of small particles $\zeta = N_s/(N_s+N_l)$ for the different monolayers studied here are summarize in Table 1. For all the mixtures studied we have found homogeneous structures without segregation: the different species distribute randomly in the lattice with no obvious pattern, demixing or significant changes in the surface number density. Occasionally, few aggregates coexist with the lattice structure.

Figure 1: Experimental microphotographs and the FFT analysis of the binary monolayers. All of them present a nearly constant surface number density value $\rho \approx 0.033$, but an increasing proportion in the number of the bigger particles (from A to J).

Monolayer	ρ_t	% ρ_s	% ρ_l	N_{sl}	ξ
A	0.039	100	0	-	1.00
B	0.027	92	8	44.40	0.98
C	0.039	77	23	12.91	0.93
D	0.031	60	40	5.79	0.85
E	0.028	45	55	3.16	0.75
F	0.036	30	70	1.66	0.62
G	0.031	16	84	0.74	0.42
H	0.030	5	95	0.20	0.17
I	0.028	1	99	0.03	0.03
J	0.038	0	100	0.00	0.00

Table 1: The total surface number density ρ_t , the partial percentages of the surface coverage $\% \rho_i = \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_t} 100$, the number ratio N_{sl} and the number fraction of small particles ξ for all the monolayers depicted in Figure 1.

Figs. 2 and 3 show the translational and orientational correlation functions of the monolayers shown in Fig. 1, which allow one to study the dependence of local and

global order on the relative concentration. Small differences in the total monolayer densities lead to spatial slight radial shifts of the distribution functions. Hence, in order to compare the distribution functions the interparticle distances r have been rescaled to r_{norm} by different constant values, matching the first peak positions with those observed in the single-component monolayers. In the range of surface coverages investigated, however, small deviations of the total surface number density do not lead to essential differences in the structures formed. 2D configurations are mainly sensitive to the relative composition and not to small changes in the total particle density⁴².

Figure 2 (color online): The translational distribution functions $g(r)$ (continuous black line), $g_{ll}(r)$ (-•- green symbols) and $g_{ss}(r)$ (-o- red symbols) of monolayers depicted in Figure 1. Inset in Figure A shows the correspondence of the peaks with the shortest and therefore most significant distances of a perfect hexagonal array. In Figure F this correspondence is shown for the main characteristic distances between two small particles (d_{ss}), two large particles (d_{ll}) and one small and one large particle (d_{sl}).

Figure 3: The orientational correlation function $g_6(r)$ of some of the monolayers depicted in Fig. 1. The dotted lines show the different decays, algebraic in monolayers B and I and exponential in monolayers C and H.

Radial and Orientational Distribution Functions

At $\rho_f = 0.033$, both single-component monolayers exhibit a solid structure (Figures 1.A and 1.J). This is confirmed by the FFT patterns that exhibit six first-order and twelve second-order diffraction peaks, asserting the high degree of hexagonal order. The corresponding translational distribution functions $g(r)$, $g_{ll}(r)$ and $g_{ss}(r)$, along with the orientational correlation function $g_\phi(r)$, are shown in Figs. 2.A, 2.J and Figs. 3.A, 3.J. Correlation functions account for the essential features of the 2D crystal lattices: pronounced oscillations and narrow peaks, equivalent to the well-established distances and orientations observed in the hexagonal array. The inset in Fig. 2.A shows the correspondence of the peaks with the shortest and therefore most significant lengths of the hexagonal crystal structure. The splitting of the second maximum into two subpeaks of nearly equal weight is a peculiar feature of high crystalline hexagonal lattices, exhibiting a proper gap width between the Voronoi nearest neighbors and the further and closer next-Voronoi nearest neighbors. Second peak splitting is less pronounced for 2D crystal formed by the bigger particles due to a slightly higher size polydispersity. On the other hand, the bond orientational correlation function approaches a constant value close to one at large separation distances, indicating a long-range order in the bond orientation.

The presence of particles of different size hinders the global crystallization of the sample. Figures 1.B-I show images and FFT analysis of binary monolayers made up with different proportions of large and small particles. Our binary systems are globally unstructured at the same high surface coverages at which monodisperse 2D systems form hexagonal crystals. Superlattices with long-range order have been recently

observed in other binary colloidal monolayers using videomicroscopy and computer simulations performed at relatively high surface coverages^{33,34,46}. Such structures have been reported in the so-called strong interaction regime where there is a high dipole strength asymmetry between large and small particles. Strong interaction strength asymmetry can be obtained by using very different sizes or/and very different surface charge densities, or strong external magnetic fields in the case of superparamagnetic particles. Those works reported a two-stage crystallization, in which the more strongly interacting components become structurally arrested first^{33,37}. Strongly interacting components self-assemble into ordered arrays, whereas the weakly interacting spheres sit at the interstices of the lattice, thus forming different binary colloidal crystals. The structure of these crystals is determined by the number ratio of the two particles. Crystallization, however, does not occur in the F, D and E monolayers even when the relative concentration nearly matches crystal stoichiometries reported in the bibliography^{33,46} (ξ close to 2/3, 3/4 and 5/6 respectively), and the monodisperse monolayers present crystalline states at similar surface densities. Relatively high value of the dipolar moment ratio, $m_{sl} \approx 0.120$, as compared with the value $m_{sl} \approx 0.037$ presented by Law et al.³³, explains why they found stable binary crystal structures whereas long-range order is not observed in our system. This m_{sl} value was calculated assuming in the different sized particles equal degree of dissociation f . When m_{sl} is too large, the presence of smaller particles distorts the large particle hexagonal sublattices, hindering the first of the two steps in the crystallization process. At high surface coverages and relatively high m_{sl} values, the impurities (*i.e.* the minority particles) enhance the distances between the predominant particles placed around them, distorting the hexagonal lattices observed in pure monolayers. Loss of the 2D perfect hexagonal array is evident by the analysis of the $g(r)$ and $g_\delta(r)$ (Figures 2.B-I and 3.B-I).

At relative low number of impurities different types of stable crystallites coexist (monolayers 1.B and 1.I, corresponding to $\xi = 0.98$ and $\xi = 0.03$). High ordered areas emerges from the tendency of the uni-component systems towards crystallization³⁷. Minority particles, however, hinder the long-range order and the global crystallization of the sample even at relatively low number concentrations. Loss of the 2D perfect hexagonal array is evident by the analysis of the $g(r)$ and $g_\delta(r)$. Radial distribution functions are similar to those corresponding to the hexagonal arrays. However, translational correlation functions of monolayer B exhibit less pronounced oscillations, a faster decay and a higher overlap of the second and third peaks. This change is much less pronounced in the monolayer I, where large majoritary particles present stronger interactions and the presence of few small particles barely disturbs the global translational order. The orientational functions $g_\delta(r)$ approach zero value at very long separation distances, and their envelope decays algebraically in both cases with a power-law $\sim r^{(-1/4)}$. Because the bond-orientational order is only quasi-long-ranged, the FFT pattern would consist of an isotropic ring. However, finite-size effects modify this pattern, so that the hexagonal pattern corresponding to a solid phase is still observed in the FFT analysis. In both monolayers the partial translational distribution function of the minority particles, with a low relative surface number density, is typical of gases: gradually increases from zero to the unity, remaining roughly constant at large enough distances. Thus, homogeneous distribution of minority particles is able to distort the long orientational order in both mixtures. The minority particles are able to perturb the hexagonal lattices even at very low number fractions, confirming that the electric dipole moment of the small particles is not much smaller than that of the large spheres.

Images 1.C and H show binary monolayers made up of a higher proportion of minority particles ($\xi = 0.93$ and $\xi = 0.17$ respectively). Upon increasing the number of impurities the softer oscillation of $g(r)$, mainly governed by the majority particle contribution, decays faster with distance. The splitting in the second peak of the translational distribution function $g(r)$ is now almost negligible, and new peaks generated by pairs of large and small particles emerge. The symmetric multiple-ring FFT patterns for these cases clearly confirm that these binary mixtures have characteristic wavelengths with wide distributions and without long-range preferred orientation. It means that long-range translational order does not exist in this system due to the polydispersity. Orientational $g_6(r)$ functions decay exponentially, $e^{-0.06r}$, and approach zero at long distances, indicating the absence of a long-range hexagonal orientational order. However, hexagonal structures persist in appearing in the binary mixture, leading to “medium-range crystalline order” (MRCO)¹.

Since the decay of $g(r)$ and $g_6(r)$ is of fundamental importance for the characterization of the different regions of the phase diagram, it is worth to remark that the experimental data have to fulfill some conditions in order to make it possible to distinguish between an exponential and an algebraic type of decay. As illustrated in the Supporting Information (Figure 1S) for $g_6(r)$ it is necessary to obtain the function from its maximum up to values of r high enough that $g(r)$ or $g_6(r)$ are zero within the experimental noise. If the functions are obtained only for a limited range of r , it will be frequently possible to fit the maxima with either an exponential or an algebraic decay. In the present work we have calculated the distribution and correlation functions up to values of r in which they have completely decayed, and thus there is no ambiguity in whether they show an exponential or an algebraic type of decay.

In mixtures D and E, made up of an increased proportion of big particles ($\xi = 0.85$ and $\xi = 0.75$) as compared with the C monolayer, tiny hexagonal crystals of varying size and orientation formed by small particles is not suppressed completely by the surrounding heterogeneous binary structure. The higher ratio of the minority particles hinders the characteristic oscillations in the $g(r)$ of the hexagonal array at large distances. Instead one observes a roughly constant value distinctive of randomly distributed configurations. At short distances first peaks account for the local configuration of the particles. The peaks in the orientational correlation function are now almost negligible (not shown in the Figure 3).

At near equimolarity, monolayers F and G ($\xi = 0.62$ and $\xi = 0.42$ respectively), the hexagonal packing of the colloidal spheres is almost completely hindered. The hexagonal orientational order decreases dramatically, and the $g(r)$ functions are almost zero for all inter-particle distances (not shown in the Figure 3). However, there is still some degree of short-range order, because the small and weaker interacting species tend to fill the interstitial sites between two big particles. Locally, some elementary structures of distorted hexagons in the large particle sublattices, branched chains of small particles, or squared body centered symmetry of big particles around a small particle are observed, accounting for the essential features of $g(r)$ ^{29,37}. The higher peak in the $g(r)$ is generated by pairs of large and small particles. Hence, the innermost next-neighbor shell formed around a particle roughly includes particles of different size in an even way. While slight short range ordering is reported no long-range order is observed which is a clear feature of highly disorder glassy or dense liquid mixtures.

Mean Square Displacements and Orientational Temporal Correlation Functions

There is no structural difference between a glass and a liquid, however, their dynamic behavior is quite different. Therefore in order to assess whether monolayers F and G correspond to a dense fluid or a glass we have studied the motion of particles in those states. The system dynamics may be quantified in real space by the single particle mean square displacement (MSD), $\langle \Delta r^2(t) \rangle = \langle (r_i(t) - r_i(0))^2 \rangle$, and the temporal orientational correlation function, $g_6(t) = \langle \varphi_{6,k}^*(t' + t) \cdot \varphi_{6,k}(t') \rangle$, that evaluates the time evolution of the orientational order. Here, $\varphi_{6,k}(t) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n e^{i6\theta_{kj}(t)}$ is the temporal local bond orientational function.

Figure 4: Mean square displacements of the solid monolayers A (empty circles) and J (empty squares), and separately plotted for big (filled square) and small colloids (filled

circle) in the highly disorder binary monolayer F. The line with unit slope represents the diffusive behavior.

In Figure 4 the MSD are separately plotted for big and small colloids in the highly disorder monolayer F and compared to those obtained in the pure crystalline systems A and J. Qualitatively, big and small colloids present similar shapes of the MSD curves in both, the crystalline solids and the disorder state. The MSDs early deviate from the diffusive motion, slowing down even at the first accessed times (~ 30 ms) and reaching a plateau for the longest measured times. This time dependence of the MSD has been widely reported in the literature as characteristic of the 2D and 3D glassy systems^{29,41,47}. As in atomic glasses, the free diffusive motion of the colloidal particles is hindered by the surrounding particles, and the particles remain arrested for long times within cages formed by their nearest-neighbor particles. Both small and large particles move in a similar way, reaching a constant MSD at the same time-range. The plateau heights correspond to the different cage sizes, which are larger for the pure monolayers formed by the small particles that have the weakest interactions.

In the Supporting Information (Figure 2S) it is shown the typical behavior of $g_\delta(t)$ for pure monolayers formed by the larger particles at different densities (experiments shown in [2]). In the crystalline phase ($\rho_t = 0.0027$) $g_\delta(t)$ is constant and close to unity, which indicates that the orientational order is conserved for long times. In the hexatic phase ($\rho_t = 5.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$) the bond orientation decays on long time scales with an algebraic behavior. In the isotropic fluid phase ($\rho_t = 1 \cdot 10^{-5}$) $g_\delta(t)$ shows exponential behavior that decays to zero, which indicates the loss of the orientational order at long times². In the disordered equimolar monolayer F the orientational correlation function $g_\delta(t)$ is close to

zero as in the liquid phase, but this value remains roughly constant in time as in the crystalline phase. In this case, the orientational correlation function was calculated taken into account bonds between all the particles present in the binary mixture. Similar dynamical behavior was found in the monolayer G. Even though the present MSD or $g_6(t)$ results alone do not allow to distinguish between crystalline and solid amorphous phases, the simultaneous discussion of the decay of the $g(r)$ and $g_6(r)$ functions and of the MSD and $g_6(t)$ data allows to make unambiguously such a distinction. According to the previous results, the highly disordered equimolar monolayers F and G can be classify as glasses, where big and small particles cage each other topologically, with liquid-like structure but with particle dynamics frozen at experimental times.

Phase Diagram

The analysis of the distribution functions reveals that the relative intensity of the peaks mainly depends on the relative number concentration, as expected. The ratio between the intensity of the higher peaks present in the total correlation functions and the partial translational correlation functions of the majority particles, $\Gamma_{ii} \equiv (g_{max}(r)) / g_{iimax}(r) (i = s, l)$, along with the intensity of the first maximum of the bond-orientational correlation function, $g_6(r)_{max}$, are shown in Figure 5 as function of the number fraction of small particles ξ . Both functions follow an almost symmetric tendency around $\xi \approx 0.6$ $g_6(r)_{max}$ and decrease with the number of impurities present in the binary mixture, as lattices loss the hexagonal orientational order. In the region II with low impurity concentrations, approximately in the intervals from $\xi > 0$ to $\xi < 0.03$ and from $\xi > 0.98$ to $\xi < 1$, $g_6(r)$ decays algebraically and the system presents a quasi-

long-range bond orientational order. The region with neither long-range translational nor hexagonal orientational order can be separated into two different phases divided by two minima in Γ_{ii} located at $\xi \approx 0.38$ and 0.8 . These two minima correspond to binary mixtures in which tiny hexagonal crystals of varying size and orientation formed by majority particles persist. This type of structure has been mentioned by Maret et al.³⁷ in the case of monolayers of superparamagnetic particles in an external magnetic field. A main difference with the present system is that their system was in the strong interaction regime, and they did not reported fully amorphous phases. In the III regions, from $\xi > 0.03$ to $\xi < 0.4$ and from $\xi > 0.75$ to $\xi < 0.93$, $g_\delta(r)$ decreases exponentially and the binary mixture can considered as a fluid. In these regions, radial distribution functions $g(r)$ are mainly determined by the partial distribution functions of the majority particles, and hexagonal structures without long-range preferred orientation persist in appearing in the binary mixture. Therefore, regions having a high degree of short-range order emerge in the global disordered monolayers^{29,48}. In the equimolar region IV, from $\xi > 0.4$ to $\xi < 0.75$, short-range order, characterized by the first maxima in the total translational correlation function, mainly emerges because of pairs of different species. First maxima reach values similar to those observed in the partial correlation functions. As a consequence the Γ_{ii} function increases with the number of impurities, arriving to a secondary maximum of Γ_{ii} located at $\xi \approx 0.6$ which corresponds to the most homogeneously mixed configuration. The orientational correlation function $g_\delta(r)$ cancels for all inter-particle distances. All the above confirms the homogeneous mixing of the different types of particles and the lack of crystallization. Hence, weakly interacting binary mixtures having approximately equal number of the two different species are able to form homogenous binary amorphous systems even at relatively high surface coverages, showing only some degree of short-range positional order.

Mechanical vibrations applied directly to the liquid/liquid interface could supply the necessary energy to improve even more this homogeneity. Upon mechanical vibrations the system even could arrive to crystalline stable state, as long as that the relative concentration of the binary monolayers matches crystal stoichiometries³³. We will go into more depth about this issue in a future work.

Figure 5 (color online): Phase diagram of different sized polystyrene particles, $a_s=1.45$ μm and $a_l=2.85$ μm , absorbed at the octane/water interface. The first maxima of the bond orientational correlation functions, $g_6(r)_{\text{max}}$, and the ratio between the intensity of the higher peaks present in the total and the majority partial translational correlation functions, Γ_{ii} , are plotted against the number fraction of small particles in the binary monolayer, ζ . It is interesting to remark that the vertical dashed lines do not represent phase transition points, but only separate regions in which the monolayers studied show structures that correspond to different phases. The dotted lines are guide for the eyes.

Coordination Numbers, Lattices Defects and Particle Interactions

In the monolayers previously studied, formed by particles with radii 1.45 and 2.85 μm , the relative intensity of the peaks depends on the relative number concentration but the relative positions between the particles remain roughly constant. Ratios between the main characteristic distances, calculated from the $g_{ij}(r)$ maxima positions, are $d_{ss}/d_{sl} = (0.74 \pm 0.05)$ and $d_{ss}/d_{ll} = (0.52 \pm 0.07)$ for all the compositions. The permanent ratio of the characteristic relative distances accounts for the four foremost nearest-neighboring particle configurations or elementary triangles (ET)³⁵: equilateral triangles formed by three small or big neighbor particles, and isosceles triangles formed by two small and one large neighbor particle or vice-versa (Figure 6). The isosceles triangles formed by two small and one large particle present an angle of 40° between the segments connecting the large and the small particles, in agreement with the coordination index (CI = 9) of the big particles in monolayers with relative high ζ values (Fig 1.B, C and D). Analogously, the isosceles triangles formed from two large and one small particle have an angle of 90° between the segments of the same length connecting the small and the large particles. Accordingly, most of the small particles observed in monolayers with relative low ζ values and surrounded by large particles are fourfold (monolayer F, G and H). In monolayer I, however, the low fraction of small particles barely disturbs the lattices, and minority particles are mostly surrounded by five large particles. Finally, the equilateral triangles lead to hexagonal array of the particles in those areas placed far away of the impurities.

Figure 6: Isosceles elementary triangles (ET) formed from the main characteristic distances d_{ss} , d_{ll} and d_{sl} , calculated from the $g_{ij}(r)$ maxima positions, for the four different 3-particle combinations of big and small particles. Ratios between these characteristic distances remain constant for all the particle proportions.

The colloidal pair interactions determine the relative distances between the colloidal particles. However, finding the minimal-energy landscape in a distribution of particles is far from trivial even when the interparticle potential is as simple as a repulsive dipolar interaction³⁶. Here we present a very direct calculation which relates the monolayer structure to the pair potential in a simple manner. Pair approximations have frequently proved effective for deriving qualitative information about lattice-based models⁴⁹. In a previous work we observed that the effective pair-potentials calculated for the unicomponent monolayers, obtained with the Boltzmann inversion method, present almost identical minimum depth values, regardless of the particle size. The depth of these minima, which strongly depends on the particle contact angle, remained also unaffected by the presence of different sized particles in the binary system⁵⁰. According to these results, we match the different effective pair-dipolar potentials between particles in their minima location, $U_{sl}(d_{sl}) = U_{ss}(d_{ss}) = U_{ll}(d_{ll})$. From Eq. 7 assuming identical dissociation degree at the aqueous phase, we obtain $d_{ss}/d_{sl} = 0.74$ and $d_{ss}/d_{ll} = 0.55$, almost identical to the experimental values.

It is plausible that the coordination numbers will depend on the size ratio of the particles even though the systems remain amorphous. We have carried the study of coordination numbers and lattice defects using binary monolayers formed by two pairs of particles of different size ratios. Besides the monolayers whose behavior has been described in the previous sections, we have also studied monolayers formed by particles with radii 0.8 and 2.85 μm .

Equally good qualitative results are obtained for other binary monolayers. Figure 7 shows a different binary monolayer consisting in small s and large l polystyrene microparticles with radii of 0.8 μm and 2.85 μm , dispersed in a water/octane interface and with similar contact angles. Using the approximation assumed above, we obtain $d_{ss}/d_{sl} \approx 0.61$ and $d_{ss}/d_{ll} \approx 0.37$. These characteristic ratios will originate isosceles ET, with an angle of 36° between the segments connecting a large with two small particles, and big particles with IC=10 are expected. This prediction of the local geometry around the big particles has been experimentally confirmed (Figure 7).

Figure 7 (color online): (left) Binary monolayer consisting in small, $a_s=0.80 \mu\text{m}$, and large, $a_l=2.85 \mu\text{m}$, polystyrene microparticles with similar wetting angles dispersed in a water/octane interface. Big particles are generally surrounded by 10 nearest small neighbors, defined through the Delaunay tessellation. (right) The framed detail is amplified. Delaunay tessellation originates isosceles ETs, with an angle of 36° between the sides connecting a large with two small particles.

Figure 8 (color online): Binary lattices B and I show numerous defects, most of them pinned at minority particles and their nearest neighbors. Defects in the binary monolayers are indicated by green (CI = 4), grey (CI = 5), red (CI = 7), yellow (CI = 8), orange (CI = 9) and violet (CI = 10). Edge dislocations are depicted as dashed red lines.

Although the analysis of the radial distribution functions and the bond orientational correlation function is a good method to assess the global degree of order in the particle monolayers, it does not allow distinguishing between the different types of defects, i.e. particles with more or less than six neighbors, in the hexagonal array. We have used the Delaunay triangulation (see Figure 8) as a complementary method to analyze the defects produced by the impurities in monolayers B and I. Binary lattices show higher concentration of defects in the hexagonal lattice, most of them pinned at minority particles and their nearest neighbors.

Even when the scaling of the orientational correlation function $g_6(r)$ is consistent with a picture of KTHNY theory, approaching unity in the solid phase, decaying algebraically in the hexatic phase and exponentially in the liquid phase, the nature of the topological defects in our binary systems is more complex than that of the KTHNY picture. In effect, at high ζ values four-, eight-, nine- and tenfold particles appear, which cannot be directly classified as dislocations or disclinations. At low ζ values, however, mostly fivefold and sevenfold coordinated particles characteristic of the KTHNY theory are observed. Hence, contrary to the asserted by other authors^{46,51}, we observe how the gradual enhance in the number of the weaker interacting particles leads to a continuous disordering process of the monolayer formed by the stronger interacting particles consistent with the KTHNY melting theory, suggesting that the I monolayer can be

identified as a hexatic phase with a quasi-long-range bond orientational order. The orientational correlation function $g_6(t)$ (not shown in the figures), however, does not decay on long time scales with an algebraic behavior as in the hexatic phase but remains roughly constant in time as in the solid crystalline phase. Large particles in monolayers B are predominantly surrounded by nine small particles. The values of Ψ_9 assessed in large particles are close to unity, thus pointing to a high local orientational order in the so-called defects. Far away from large particles, the small particles present a perfect hexagonal array, with local bond-order parameter $\Psi_6 \approx 1$. In I monolayers, each small particle is generally surrounded by 5 big spheres. Here, Ψ_5 values assessed in small particles are $\Psi_5 \approx 0.75$, indicating a lower local orientational order around the impurities. In contrast with the large impurities, that strongly rearrange their local environment, the presence of a relatively low number of the small particles gently disrupts the crystal order, allowing the disordering transition of the monolayers in a soft manner consistent with the KTHNY theory.

Partial clustering prevents the homogenous distribution and the global crystallization of particles in 2D monolayers⁵². In what follows we will show that partially aggregated uni-component monolayers reproduce similar features that those observed in the binary systems. In effect, a continuous transition between the long and short-range order also takes place. Figure 9 shows typical images for the two different partially aggregated monolayers of $a_s=1.45 \mu\text{m}$ polystyrene particles, with 2% and 16% in number of primary particles forming aggregates. The presence of the small aggregates hinders the global crystallization of the sample, distorting the hexagonal lattices observed in pure monolayers. At relative low percentage of aggregates different stable crystallites formed by the non-aggregated unities coexist. Dimers and trimers are usually surrounded by

seven non-aggregated particles (Figure 9.A). As the number of aggregates enhances the orientational correlation function $g_6(r)$ passes from an algebraically to an exponentially decay, as shown in Figure 11. The number of defects in the hexagonal lattice increases with the number of aggregates and the nature of the topological defects in the partially aggregated monolayers is again more complex than the KTHNY picture (Figure 9.B). Partially aggregated monolayers reproduce the same phenomenology observed in binary systems with low interaction ratios, which seem to be a realistic model for glass-forming substances, probably showing universal features of the vitrification process in 2D.

Figure 9 (color online): 2% (A) and 16% (B) partially aggregated monolayers in a water/octane interface. Defects in the aggregated monolayers are indicated according to the color code depicted in Figure 8. The orientational correlation function $g_\delta(r)$ of the different monolayers is also depicted. The dotted lines show the different decay, algebraic in monolayers with low number of aggregates and exponential in monolayers with higher number of aggregates, as expected at continuous melting transition.

CONCLUSIONS

We have characterized the mean structural features of binary monolayers with a nearly constant surface number density $\rho_t = 0.033$, but varying the proportions of small and large particles. Homogeneous structures without segregation were found in all cases. The presence of particles of different size, and the relatively high value of the dipolar moment ratio, hinders the global crystallization exhibit by the uni-component monolayers. The presence of impurities leads to a gradual vitrification of the system, and the local hexagonal order continuously becomes extinct from the crystal solid to the glassy equimolar state. During the disordering process the length scaling of the orientational correlation function $g_\delta(r)$ is consistent with a picture of KTHNY theory. In contrast with monodisperse systems, mixtures having approximately equal number of the two different species form homogenous binary glasses at relatively high surface coverages, with only some degree of subtle short-range positional order. As the number of impurities is unbalanced, the majority particles in the glass monolayer begin to dispose into small hexagonal crystallites, and the system is locally less disordered than in the equimolar stoichiometry. A phase diagram of the system was established by the

careful use of translational and correlation functions. The amorphous region, with no long range order, can be separated into two different phases: a homogeneously mixed phase and other phase where hexagonal arranged structures formed by the majority particles persist.

Even when the relative intensity of the peaks is determined by the relative number concentration, their relative positions remain roughly constant. The permanent ratio of the characteristic relative distances accounts for the four foremost nearest-neighboring particle configurations or elementary triangles (ET). We have presented a direct calculation which relates the monolayer structure to the pair potential in a simple manner and allows foreseeing the local structure of other binary mixtures of colloidal particles. We have used the Delaunay triangulation as a complementary method to analyze the defects produced by the impurities in monolayers. Although all of the above are consistent with a picture of KTHNY theory melting through two transitions and an intermediate hexatic phase, the nature of the topological defects in our binary systems is more complex than the KTHNY picture. Under a gradual enhance in the number of the weaker interacting particles, however, mostly fivefold and sevenfold coordinated particles characteristic of the KTHNY melting theory are observed and consequently the binary system seems to melt through a hexatic phase with a quasi-long-range bond orientational order. Finally, we have corroborated that binary systems with low interaction ratios represent a realistic model for glass-forming substances, comparing the previous results with those obtained in partially aggregated monolayer. This work may serve as a benchmark for further dynamical studies on melting, vitrification and crystal nucleation in 2D.

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Supporting Information Available: Spatial and temporal decays of the orientational correlation function. This material is available free of charge via the internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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